

POLITICAL RAP: A FORM OF BLACK POLITICAL PARTICIPATION IN AN ERA OF
MODERN PROTEST

by

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6653935

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton
May 2022

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Date:

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6/9/22

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5/31/2022

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Abstract

Political rap is an art form used to protest to dismantle oppressive practices within the American government. Hip-hop is a movement rooted in political power that addresses various social justice issues within the Black community, ranging from mass incarceration to police brutality. Pioneers of Political Rap insist on publicly deconstructing injustice to empower Black youth to understand their position in society is not determined by government structures. This paper encompasses Political Rap as a form of symbolic protest through its nonviolent, public, and deliberate commentary on American law and social practices to educate the social sphere on current injustices not known to the public. This paper discusses each generation of Political Rap, ranging from the 1970s, 1980s, 1990s, 2000s, and 2010s; each period will focus on Political raps protesting implemented laws that culminate in social injustices. The 1970s explores the Black Power movement and Political rap's introduction, the 1980s and the golden age of hip-hop, the 1990s and the prison industrial complex, the 2000s, the effects capitalism has on rap music, and the 2010s and the Black Lives Matter movement. The final study concludes Political Rap's connection to Black activities through evidence referenced in Christopher J. Lebron's *The Making of Black Lives Matter: A Brief History of an Idea* (2017), S. Craig Watson's *Hip-Hop Matters* (2005), Jeffery O.G. Ogbar's *Hip-Hop Revolution: The Culture and Politics of Rap* (2007), Bakari Kitwana's *The Hip-Hop Generation* (2002), and a culmination of peer-reviewed works. Black Americans have created their political sphere by using conscious rap to showcase anti-racism and anti-poverty by exploring artists like Afrika Bambaataa, Public Enemy, N.W.A., Ice Cube, and Kendrick Lamar. Overall, the study examines how conscious rap made a difference for the Black community.

Keywords: political rap, conscious rap, politics, hip-hop, injustice, race relations

Political Rap: A Form of Black Political Participation in an Era of Modern Protest

The emergence of Hip-hop as a generational movement and genre has forever changed how Americans consume and interpret American culture. Hip-hop historians trace the first implications of hip-hop, also referred to as rap, to the early 1970s, which was directly influenced by activism in the Black Power movement while establishing its roots in the Bronx, New York. Hip-hop combines deejaying and turntablism, delivery and lyricism of rapping and emceeing, forms of dance, and graffiti art and writing to evolve hip-hop knowledge (Morgan and Bennett, 2011, pg. 177). Hip-hop knowledge combines the previously listed elements to define an aesthetic made of social, intellectual, and political identities, beliefs, behaviors, and values to be further cultivated. These implications constructed hip-hop as a voice for younger generations to comment on social and economic issues affecting their everyday lives. All three interpretations of hip-hop as a genre, generation, and movement must be interpreted appropriately to understand its political implications.

Hip-hop as a generation. Hip-hop culture has had a significant influence on the younger generation of Americans, extending globally due to the genre's commercialization. Political analyst and activist Bakari Kitwana identify this newly emerging Black youth as "Black America's generation X".¹ Kitwana states that Black youth collected cultural aspects through traditional communal institutions between the 1920s and the 1960s, including the church, school, family, and peers. Rather than creating a Black identity through these common institutions, this generation of youth could use hip-hop to express their political ideas to empower the Black family dynamic, social responsibilities, and Black pride.² The hip-hop generation is comprised

¹ Kitwana (2002). *The Hip-Hop Generation: Young Blacks and the Crisis in African-American Culture*. Basic Books. p. 7

² Kitwana (2002). *The Hip-Hop Generation: Young Blacks and the Crisis in African-American Culture*, pg. 7

of multiracial, multiethnic, and multilingual individuals from diverse classes, genders, and sexual identities (Morgan and Bennett, 2011, pg. 177). The issues regarding Black pride and civil rights were still a concern for the hip-hop generations, like their parent's generation before them. Still, they could express their concerns through authentic self-presentation and aesthetic ethos.

In addition to the rights and social ranking earned by the generation before them, the hip-hop generationers differ from their parents and grandparents, considering the hip-hop generation has a more flexible worldview. Views on social ideologies were influenced by the legal rights they obtained. Complimentary to this, Kitwana (2002) notes:

We... are more likely than our parents' generation to be obsessed with our careers and getting rich quick. For us, achieving wealth, by any means necessary, is more important than anything else, hence our obsession with the materialistic and consumer trappings of financial success.³

At the same time, the hip-hop generation redefines other ideologies considering their perspective on family and relationships are open to family arrangements instead of the American family structure.⁴ This generation's socio-political identity was also influenced by current politically charged events, bearing "Jesse Jackson's 1984 and 1988 presidential campaigns, the 1922 Los Angeles riots, the Million Man March...and H.I.V./Aids" in the Black community.⁵ These young Black Americans were also impacted by globalization, the racially charged criminal justice system, and a public ban on Black American culture, including hair and dress styles.⁶

As America's outcasts, generalized conditions affected the hip-hop generationers, and the quality of life for Black youth diminished despite their legal promise. The hip-hop generationers experienced class warfare that paralleled the political climate of the 1960s because Black youth

³Ibid. pg. 6-15

⁴Ibid.

⁵Ibid.

⁶Ibid.

were still searching for social justice.⁷ The motivations for nonviolent civil disobedience were disregarded, considering police brutality, racial inequalities, and economic inequality defined class and race indifferences.⁸ Drugs and crime influenced racial animosity towards Black Americans, specifically Black men, and law enforcement and media's influence on the perception of Black culture. The crack epidemic and low-wage-low-skill level jobs exhausted Black inferiority to justify the negative connotations placed on Black people.⁹ These factors contributed to police brutality due to militarized policing tactics built to stop the drug trade and gang activity.¹⁰ As a response, militarized policing tactics were encouraged by Ronald Reagan's 1971 War on Drugs and Bill Clinton's 1994 Crime Bill, which maintained America's fear of Black superpredators¹¹.

Based on the findings presented, African Americans born between 1965 and 1984 developed a complex worldview considering family, relationships, children, careers, racial identity, race relations, and politics, which readjusted this group as hip-hop generationers. Hip-hop generationers flourished in the 1980s because rap artists communicated their socio-political opinion through unorthodox styles of rebellion to infiltrate the American political sphere. Their influence then inspired filmmakers, photographers, producers, scholars, publishers, writers, and activists who expanded hip-hop into a political movement.

Hip-hop as a genre. A key aspect discussed in hip-hop is the musical characteristics that establish it as a genre in art. The hip-hop genre combines lyrics and beats to mimic the folkloric

⁷Kitwana, *The Hip-Hop Generation: Young Blacks and the Crisis in African-American Culture*, p. 37-44

⁸ Ibid, pg. 11

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ Ibid.

¹¹ Sims, Preston, P., & Sims, B. (Barbara A. . (2006). *Handbook of juvenile justice : theory and practice*. CRC/Taylor & Francis. The superpredator myth was described as groups of juveniles that engage in brutal crimes against other people, operate with no remorse, and are an urban nightmare. The term was coined by James Wootton, the president of the Safe Streets Coalition.

traditions of African Americans.¹² Hip-hop is an oppositional art that seeks to use music to inform the public about present injustices and unlawful activity committed by American government institutions.¹³ The complexity of hip-hop has exceeded all expectations over the decades. It has required artists to stay true to hip-hop's five musical elements to maintain their realness and authenticity.¹⁴ The hip-hop generationers developed the five elements during the 1970s; thus, supporting an artist's realness was based on their ability to stay true to them. Any individual engaging in hip-hop had to pick their niche in emceeing (MCing), deejaying (DJing), b-boying, graffiti, and beatboxing (B.A.M., n.d.). A few of the elements existed before others, but each aspect fed off another to cultivate a distinguished foundation for ghetto expression. The deejay was one of the elements that existed before hip-hop and became the acronym for disc jockey.¹⁵ The deejay played for a live or radio audience and made rhythmic songs for emcees to rap over through turntablism.¹⁶ The Master of Ceremonies, or emcee, used rhythmic call-and-response to draw an audience's attention. Under the influence of spoken-word artists, an emcee developed their poetic delivery, or flow, to communicate. Most deejays began as beatboxers, so as turntables became more popular, they subsequently turned away from making beats with their mouths. The final two elements, graffiti and b-boying are the more physical artistic manifestations of hip-hop and can be more seen than heard.¹⁷

Of all the elements, deejaying and emceeing have developed the most over the decades; deejaying evolved into soundboards and emceeing into rap as globalization spread throughout America. The commercialization of hip-hop influenced the technological advancements that

¹² Ogbar, J. (2007). *Hip-hop Revolution: The Culture and Politics of Rap*. University Press of Kansas. p. 13

¹³ Ibid, pg. 39

¹⁴ Kitwana, *The Hip-Hop Generation: Young Blacks and the Crisis in African-American Culture*, p. 11

¹⁵ BAM, https://www.bam.org/media/5500824/Elements_of_Hip-hop.pdf

¹⁶ Fonseca and Goldsmith (2021). *Listen to Hip Hop! Exploring A Musical Genre*. ABC-CLIO, LLC., pg. 1-3

¹⁷ Ibid, pg 3

followed. The underground deejaying sound on turntables was not clear enough for the radio, so when labels took an interest in artists, they cultivated the artist's sound with advanced soundboards and equipment. Emcees had to develop their freestyling into organized rapping to parallel the progressive sound.

According to Anthony J. Fonseca and Melissa Ursula Dawn Goldsmith (2021), "Rap involves spoken vocals that typically feature rhyme, alliteration, assonance, wordplay, and imagery, all used to express an idea, message, or other kinds of content musically." A.J. Fonseca and M.U.D. Goldsmith also mentions that M.C.s, or rappers, use street slang and urban idioms, including high-energy, jazzy, and aggressive rhyme talking.¹⁸ Early rappers mastered freestyling in rap battles, recorded rap, and themes about romance, sex, money, and partying to organize old-school rap.¹⁹ The rapper must balance a complex rhyme (multiple end or internal rhyme) over a quadruple meter or a four-by-four beat signature. Rapping stuck to its poetic roots by being influenced by poets like Scott-Heron and M.C.s like The Last Poets; they directly highlighted the rhythmic tradition through jazz poetry. Jazz's highly rhythmic and emotional expression articulates an informative and energizing tone that hip-hop has repurposed for artistic gain.²⁰

Besides the rhythmic skill, rap requires knowledge about how the lyrics are delivered, otherwise known as flow. A.J. Fonseca and M.U.D. Goldsmith (2021) briefly outlines that a rapper's flow can range from fast-paced and aggressive to laid-back and chant-like. In the mid-1980s, artists expressed socio-political issues, dealing with drugs, violence, activism, and police brutality, through more rhyme and melodic line.²¹ Further in the 1990s, rappers evolved to

¹⁸ Fonseca and Goldsmith, *Listen to Hip Hop! Exploring A Musical Genre*, pg. 1-3

¹⁹ *Ibid.* pg. 2

²⁰ *Ibid.* pg. 3

²¹ *Ibid.*

implement gangsta rap as another delivery category. Gangsta rap combines urban lifestyles, like crime, drugs, sex, murder, and melodic rhythm and sound.²² The advancement of hip-hop has seen many developments since its incorporation in the 1970s. However, no matter the delivery or rhythmic choice, rap communicates an artist's opinion through a melodic conveyance.

Hip-hop as a movement. Combining people, music, and politics ultimately established intergenerational activism, and rappers redefined themselves as socially responsible for the Black community. The hip-hop movement struggled to take form due to young Black Americans' inability to organize at a national level. Firstly, the hip-hop generationers evolved when Black Americans could fulfill their American Dream²³ and gain economic stability. The rights acquired during the Civil Rights era make the hip-hop generation privileged due to their access to equal opportunity and careers unavailable to the previous generation.²⁴ Next, this generation of Black youth did not have a mass political movement that generalized concerns in the Black community. The Black Power and Civil Rights era had a broad-based movement that contested injustices harbored by classical racism; in contrast, the previous generation recognized anti-racism and anti-war activism. Despite the absence of a national movement, the Black community has various "smaller-scale activist movements"²⁵ surrounding police brutality, the criminal justice system, and the incarceration system. The hip-hop generation did not have a cohesive political movement to follow since a minority of hip-hop generationers cultivated their legal rights through consumerism and job opportunity. "Pursuing financial security through careers in the mainstream economy and... the underground economy... have taken priority over activist'

²² Ibid, pg. 3

²³ "The American Dream is a national ethos of the United States, a set of ideals in which freedom includes the opportunity for prosperity and success, and an upward social mobility achieved through hard work" from <https://www.proquest.com/wire-feeds/ej-sterling-llc-reviews-definition-american-dream/docview/1503271894/se-2?accountid=9840>

²⁴ Kitwana, *The Hip-Hop Generation: Young Blacks and the Crisis in African-American Culture*, pg. 147-150

²⁵ Ibid, pg. 148-149

concerns for most hip-hop generationers”.²⁶ The economic expansions witnessed through the 1980s and the 1990s distracted most young Black Americans who conformed to careers over activism.²⁷ In other words, submission over freedom. In addition, the hip-hop movement struggled since the evolution of political thought transcended traditional political boundaries between generations. Black American identity is characterized by being a revolutionary or nationalist perspective. This phenomenon has caused Black youth to align with conservatism or the Independent Party and disassociate with the liberal Democratic party.²⁸ The self-help, American Dream, nationalist perspective affiliated with issues surrounding less government and less welfare promised through conservatism provides stability most Black Americans hadn’t experienced before receiving equal rights from Constitutional amendments. Finally, the desire for political dissent has been discouraged by the vilification of Black activism. Kitwana (2002)

notes:

Including shoot-outs between police and activists groups like the Black Panthers, police-instigated battles between activist camps... the assassinations of Dr. Martin Luther King Jr., Medgar Evers, Malcolm X, and others, and the imprisonment... of activists... have discouraged this generation of activists as well.²⁹

The disenfranchisement caused by the isolation theory³⁰ determines that Black Americans have been strategically removed from political discourse influenced by interior and exterior drawbacks. Despite this phenomenon, political rap introduced another form of political participation theory. The ethnic community theory³¹ established an oppositional culture that

²⁶ Kitwana, *The Hip-Hop Generation: Young Blacks and the Crisis in African-American Culture*, pg. 154

²⁷ Ibid, pg. 154

²⁸ Ibid, pg. 150

²⁹ Ibid, pg. 153

³⁰ “Isolation theory... argues a direct race effect based on... structural barriers such as structural barriers such as threats of violence and disenfranchisement techniques are considered direct obstacles to Black voting and other modes of political expressions”: Danigelis, Black Political Participation in the United States: Some Recent Evidence from *American Sociological Review*, 1978, pg. 757

³¹ “Ethnic community theory”: Danigelis, Black Political Participation in the United States: Some Recent Evidence from *American Sociological Review*, 1978, pg. 757

explored the artistic authenticity of Black Americans combined with political ideas. Emphasized through ethnic community theory is an ideology that after experiencing structural barriers, Black Americans will seek refuge within their ethnic community and produce social cohesion and unity.³² The unifying characteristics of ethnic community theory “argues that discrimination produces not lower but higher levels of political efficacy and interest, and, therefore, of political participation among Blacks” (Danigelis, 1978, pg. 757). Political rap exemplifies ethnic community theory by existing as a vessel for a cohesive form of activism to showcase political participation. The hip-hop movement cultivated political rap by unifying the Black community under one art form, and the Black community used rap to infiltrate other areas of popular American culture. Complementary to this, Black Americans canceled out the alienation and isolation of American culture under the hip-hop movement through an ethnically exclusive campaign.

Political Rap and American Politics.

As previously mentioned in the last section, through the ethnic community theory, Black Americans could expand political rap as a rebellious art form that expresses their political opinions. The conventional political activities, like voting and town hall meetings, that are practiced in a legal sphere are exchanged with rhyme and style. Despite the commercialization of hip-hop in the 1990s, hip-hop has maintained political discourse since it emerged as a musical genre. The hip-hop generationers retained the political messages communicated through the Civil Rights and Black Power movements but established their ethnic standards in the Afrocentric and Gangsta rap movements. In addition, non-Black contributions to political rap through White and Latino artists have acknowledged their ethnic community’s challenges and the condition of

³² Ibid. 757-758

Black Americans. This trend has led to intersectionality across ethnic lines well past the 2010s era of political rap.

Rap artists use the musical components to stress political themes regarding police brutality, poverty, mass incarceration, gun violence, “gangbanging”, partying, income disparities, and gender inequalities. The Billboard “Hot Rap Songs” chart recorded that approximately twelve percent of songs mentioned political references over thirty years, beginning in 1989 (O’Connor, 2018). During the 1990s, specifically in 1991, about thirty-three percent of rap songs had political concerns (O’Connor 2018). The over-commercialization of hip-hop caused the 2000s and 2010s to see the lowest percentage of political rap songs; despite this change, in 2017, political messages returned to rap music in thirty-three percent of songs (O’Connor 2018). Years ranging from 2000, 2004, 2006, 2010, and 2011 only met ten percent of political messages (O’Connor 2018).

Based on the findings presented by O’Connor, political messages are prominent in conscious rap and can spread ideas as an informal discussion about controversial topics. The hip-hop generationers target political discourse to respond to the “historical oppression and injustices experienced by minority groups”.³³ The rebellious attitudes expressed through political rap extend on a global scale. Political rap appeals to youth internationally, considering it can protest injustices against immigrants and ethnic minorities besides Black Americans. Even before political rap’s inauguration, political tension has existed between Black Americans and the American government. The *Pew Research Center* (2021) reported that the 117th Congress was the most racially and ethnically diverse in the history of Congress, with twenty-three percent sitting minority members (Schaeffer, 2021). Black Americans have used socially conscious rap

³³ Fonseca and Goldsmith. *Listen to Hip Hop! Exploring A Musical Genre*, pg. 217

to express their political ideas because their minority is vastly underrepresented in government institutions. Each era since political rap's birth represents an era of political attitudes expressed through elements of hip-hop culture, including rap, graffiti, fashion, and production.

The 1970s: A Pioneer of Political Rap.

The origins of the hip-hop movement are traced back to the 1970s in the “Boogie Down Bronx” of New York City.³⁴ The 1970s was a crucial era for rap as rap was “unsullied, unburdened, and unchained by the commercial forces and political divisions”³⁵ that affected the hip-hop movement after commercialization of the genre. The social and economic forces expanded the underground rap scene into new identities and art forms for young Black Americans during this period. The hip-hop movement began as an organic act of expressionism that progressed into a nation of empowerment and social change³⁶. The emergence of hip-hop was mainly attributed to the increasing desire for Black communities to be adequately represented in the American entertainment industry. The portrayal of Black Americans did not accurately represent African culture because of stereotypical images of the minstrel and mammy and the criminalization of Black Americans in the media. These hostile and demeaning images often “operated as a racial reference for Whites of various classes”³⁷, thus maintaining that Black Americans were incapable of making decisions for themselves in life. These caricatures reinforced White supremacy and justified the sociopolitical status preserving the racial hierarchy and placing Black Americans below Whites. Hip-hop was a new art form rooted in Black culture

³⁴ “Boogie Down Bronx” is term naïve to the Bronx, New York, used to describe the early hip-hop era: Watkins, *Hip Hop Matters: Politics Pop Culture, and the Struggle for the Soul of a Movement*, Beacon Press Books, 2005, pg. 1

³⁵ Watkins, *Hip Hop Matters Politics, Pop Culture, and the Struggle for the Soul of a Movement*, pg. 9

³⁶ *Ibid*, pg. 10

³⁷ *Ibid*, pg. 13

and controlled by Black people, aimed to protest the racist depictions of the ethnic community in American media.

The Harlem Renaissance is a radical Black art movement where agents of social change advocated for refined Black creative art and reintroduced Black civic engagement (Lebron, 2017). These agents ranged from novelists, poets, dramatists, and visual artists who wanted to make Black political art influential and relevant. Philosophers like Alain Locke, the originator of the new negro, Langston Hughes, who used jazz and blues for Black uplift, and Zora Neale Hurston, who used Black folklore for Black uplift, developed the renaissance era and analyzed the political possibilities within art (Lebron, 2017, pg. 37). Each philosopher developed differing ideas on reaching Black uplift, but each theory sought to assert Black Americans in the political sphere. The Harlem Renaissance showed how Black Americans wanted inclusion and democratic acceptance, thus beginning an era of rebellion through art forms.

The revolutionary era of the Black Power movement asserted how Black Americans demanded proper representation in every aspect of American culture, and stereotypical images became the antithesis of hip-hop.³⁸ As the birthplace of hip-hop, New York sent a message to White audiences that racist imagery, through songs like “De New York Nigger”³⁹, would no longer misrepresent the beauty of Black culture and Black art.

One of the first rappers to acknowledge rap’s political ability was Afrika Bambaataa, born Kevin Donovan in New York. Afrika Bambaataa matured in the South Bronx during the early 1970s when street culture, fostered by gangs, dominated the community. Units like the Puerto Rican Savage Skulls and African American Black Spades would terrorize their zones by

³⁸ Watkins, *Hip Hop Matters Politics, Pop Culture, and the Struggle for the Soul of a Movement*, pg. 17

³⁹ *Ibid*, pg. 17

stealing, intimidating, and harassing anyone.⁴⁰ Afrika Bambaataa indulged in gang activity in his early years, and as hip-hop grew in the community, so did Bambaataa's interests in the genre. Afrika Bambaataa's extensive resume includes "a wide palette of musical styles...including German techno, calypso, as well as disco, rock, and soul".⁴¹ As time progressed, Bambaataa comprehended that hip-hop could constitute an activist role by empowering the youth to use it to their political and artistic advantage.

Bambaataa's growing reputation as a pioneering D.J. permitted him to repurpose gang culture's energy, loyalty, and passion into positive representations of social activity.⁴² Bambaataa hosted block and house parties to enhance community life and engagement to incorporate his love for music and b-boying with activist ventures, like establishing his reformist group Zulu Nation.⁴³ Bambaataa affirmed that his parties discouraged drug dealers by violently driving them out of the area. Equally important, Zulu Nation vowed anti-violence and unity to create a positive group instead of a gang.⁴⁴ The inauguration of the Zulu Nation was inspired by the 1964 film *Zulu* for its interpretation of "Black people fighting for what was theirs against the British".⁴⁵ The Zulu Nation, or warriors for the community, conducted meetings about discipline, eradicating drugs and violence, and provided an open forum for ideas to improve the housing projects. Bambaataa ran their political business in his flamboyant clothing and hairstyles while encouraging Black Americans to contribute to their community in a unified and organized political participation. Bambaataa spread political ideologies through hip-hop culture and

⁴⁰ Ibid, pg. 22

⁴¹ Ibid, pg 17

⁴² Ibid, pg. 22-23

⁴³ Ibid, pg. 22-23

⁴⁴ Ibid, pg. 22-23

⁴⁵ Afrika Bambaataa as quoted Ibid, pg. 23

repurposed hip-hop's energy towards a productive lifestyle by mobilizing young people and discussing current injustices.

Afrika Bambaataa's music and community ties marked him as a prominent actor in the hip-hop movement's history. His fans and peers remember him as a constructive commodity. The early elements of hip-hop further evolved due to its availability to the broader public after 1979. The next era defined the increasingly commercial effects and the evolving ideologies within hip-hop culture.

The 1980s: The Golden Age of Hip-Hop.

In the 1980s, otherwise known as the golden age of hip-hop, Black artists continued their mission to eradicate the Black community's stereotypes, thus introducing forms of Black authenticity or realness that rappers interpreted as their philosophy. Black Americans became inherently aware of the contemporary images showcased by White supremacy. The universal demand for an accurate representation of Black life meant not to erase the Black criminal or coon. Still, to remove the dominance those images had as Black representation in the entertainment industry.

It can be understood that realness attributes to the "intimate familiarity with the urban, working-class landscapes that gave rise to hip-hop in the 1970s".⁴⁶ If a rapper did not resonate with the hardships commonly attached to the Black community, they were not faithful to hip-hop roots. The struggles synonymous with poor living, drugs, gangs, and toxic relationships were a few examples of the many ties a rapper could identify with, while suburban living and Whiteness are removed from hip-hop's ideological framework.⁴⁷ In the late 1980s, however, Black Americans of varying economic and social backgrounds were inclined to join the hip-hop

⁴⁶ Ogbar, J. (2007). *Hip-hop Revolution: The Culture and Politics of Rap*. Pg. 39

⁴⁷ Ibid, pg. 39

movement for rap's ability to break mainstream barriers in contemporary radio attributed to record companies.⁴⁸ Despite the convergence of hip-hop into modern urban radio, pre-contemporary radio standards prompted "no rap promos" on public stations to resist the genre's youthful exuberance, authentic style, and activist possibilities.⁴⁹

Public Enemy and N.W.A. characterized the 1980s rap scene to rebel against the social and political status quo reflected through Black nationalist affirmations, Black authenticity, and street-level gangsta rhetoric.⁵⁰ The new activism explored in this era heightened rap's popularity and expressed a neoliberal ideology that was finally encouraged by institutions outside of the Black community. The political links to rap amplified in 1984 and 1988. Artists like "Melle Mel, DJ Magnificent, Afrika Bambaataa... performed on behalf of the presidential campaigns of Jesse Jackson and the mayoral campaign of David Dinkins".⁵¹ The political gains of rap in the 80s did not overshadow the issues in the era. The "positive" messages endorsed in political rap often analyzed crime, unemployment, drugs, the criminal system, and the American democracy. Foundational to this, the condition of Black life had outer influences that directly and indirectly affected their quality of life. Ronald Reagan's economic policies endorsed tax breaks and incentives for big corporations, so, consequently, the Black unemployment rate rose to 18.9 percent.⁵² After big corporations went abroad and deindustrialized the country, there was a rise in crack cocaine and deadly violence, and thousands of Black Americans died.⁵³ The politically conscious rappers of this era wanted to improve the condition of their communities by warning young Blacks about the dangers of criminal and drug lifestyles.

⁴⁸ Watkins, *Hip Hop Matters Politics, Pop Culture, and the Struggle for the Soul of a Movement*, pg. 78

⁴⁹ *Ibid*, pg. 79

⁵⁰ Ogbar, J., *Hip-hop Revolution: The Culture and Politics of Rap*, pg. 56

⁵¹ *Ibid*, pg. 146

⁵² *Ibid*, pg. 145

⁵³ *Ibid*, pg. 145

Public Enemy and N.W.A. used their political rap careers to embody the two main ideologies behind Black activism. Public Enemy approached conscious rap by pursuing political consciousness through radical traditions maintained by Black militancy and encouraged radical Black thinking in the political sphere.⁵⁴ While N.W.A. approaches the same strategies, their political consciousness is expressed through street-level violence that reflects the hip-hop generationer's disdain for the institutions governing their ethnic community.⁵⁵ These archetypes spoke for themselves throughout each rap group's discography and criticized White supremacy, prisons, political corruption, and police brutality. Public Enemy's 1988 album, *It Takes a Nation of Millions to Hold Us Back*, "raised the bar of social criticism".⁵⁶ This expanded Black political participation by showcasing to Black Americans that their political desires should matter. The Black experience was personified as other ethnic communities gained access to the genre. The Black militancy reflected by Public Enemy's artwork included songs Ogbar (2007) mentions, like:

Black Steel in the Hour of Chaos' raised the bar for critical race discourse and the prison industry as it explained how the song's protagonist was arrested for refusing to join the 'army or whatever' for a government that 'never gave a damn about a brother like me.'⁵⁷ Members of Public Enemy, like Chuck D, also correlate the state prison to another "form of slavery" in the same song. Chuck D describes being arrested for the radical politics he claims is a threat to the American political hierarchy and describes the Black community as an "oasis of freedom for a group of inmates".⁵⁸ The 1988 album also references Black activists turned prisoners from the Black Power era, like Huey Newton, Eldridge Cleaver, Bobby Seale, and Assata Shakur, and endorses political figures like Nelson Mandela. Further evidence

⁵⁴ Ibid, p. 147-149

⁵⁵ Ibid, pg. 147

⁵⁶ Ibid, pg. 105

⁵⁷ Ibid, pg. 146

⁵⁸ Ibid, pg. 146

demonstrates “Public Enemy’s ‘Night of the Living Baseheads’ detailed the effects of the crack trade and political corruption and sampled Nation of Islam minister Khalid Muhammad.⁵⁹ Public Enemy’s 1990 Grammy Award for the 1990 song “Fight the Power” demonstrated how rap could be socially relevant, conscious, and commercially successful. Public Enemy made political discussions readily available to the Black community and exposed the community’s frustrations.⁶⁰

N.W.A. (Niggaz with Attitudes) expressed Black nationalist ideologies, but their approach to activism took direct action through its lyrics. Unlike Public Enemy, N.W.A.’s lyrics reflected violent imagery about Black life through an aggressive style. The rap group gave communities outside of Los Angeles a view into the hardships of the city. The expansion of New York hip-hop to the West Coast can be attributed to the Great Migration in which Black Americans, between 1910 and 1970, moved out of the American South and into Northern, Midwestern, and Western states. Black Americans established themselves on the West Coast, and the community’s political position was no better than that of their counterparts on the East Coast. Hip-hop on the West Coast evolved the traditional elements into the new gangsta rap style by 1988, and the technique had an increasingly harsh tone and graphic storytelling. Individuals on the West Coast also experienced “dire conditions... of... rising unemployment, declining social programs, police terror, institutionalized racism, crime, and burgeoning drug trade”.⁶¹ Gangsta rappers provided narratives that personified stories they knew individuals around them lived. Instead of placing general messages in their music, gangsta artists would display the everyday lives they’d lived. N.W.A.’s debut studio album *Straight Outta Compton*

⁵⁹ Ibid, pg. 109

⁶⁰ Watkins, *Hip Hop Matters Politics, Pop Culture, and the Struggle for the Soul of a Movement*, pg. 119

⁶¹ Ogbar, J., *Hip-hop Revolution: The Culture and Politics of Rap*, pg. 109

(1988) specifically provided political discourse about American institutions profiting off Black lives, race relations between Black and White Americans, the effects of the prison industrial complex on the Black community, and the harsh realities of Black life. The gangsta rap subgenre was outside the scope of commercially acceptable rap music, yet N.W.A. made record labels, like Ruthless Records and Interscope Records, a remarkable amount of money. Further evolution of the gangsta rap style outflowed into the 1990s, where it saw the most significant contributions by Ice Cube.

While still a part of N.W.A., Ice Cube, alongside Eazy-E, DJ. Ren, Dr. Dre, and D.J. Yella would revel in misogyny and violence⁶². Take, for instance, “Gangsta Gangsta” from the album *Straight Outta Compton* (1988). The group raps about shootings and beatings and further acknowledges that they “never shoulda been let out the penitentiary”.⁶³ The rappers refer to Black men and women using derogatory terms and ultimately reinforce the stereotype that Black men are criminals. However, the song conveys that the prison industrial complex negatively affects the Black community by circulating individuals through the prison system and reinforcing violence. N.W.A. explored the power relationship between African Americans and the Los Angeles Police Department.

Moreover, the group comments on the “demand for justice from a racist police officer”.⁶⁴ These political messages resonated with Los Angeles Black youth since most were the subject of racial profiling. Gangsta rap expressed through violent imagery created a unique art form and political consciousness, thus bringing success to the artists martyring themselves for the cause.

⁶² “Ice Cube broke from N.W.A. in 1989 after a dispute with payments and the business tactics of manager Jerry Heller, who along with Eric “Eazy-E” Wright, controlled Ruthless Records and the group”: Ogbar, *Hip-hop Revolution: The Culture and Politics of Rap*, pg. 152

⁶³ Ibid, pg. 148

⁶⁴ Ibid, pg. 151

Political rap was reaching new heights during the golden age of hip-hop. Public Enemy achieved Grammy-award winning status, and N.W.A. gained platinum-level sales. However, the public, specifically government actors like the F.B.I., would deny gangsta rap as a healthy exercise of political expression. Conscious rap extended into the 1990s through gangsta rap, and hip-hop was creeping towards its commercial peak despite the public disdain.

The 1990s: Gangsta Rap.

Gangsta rap emerged in 1988, but the rebellious sound extended well into the 1990s and 2000s. Although not inherently political, political rap activists used gangsta rap to express conscious ideology about gang life, drugs, prostitution, and homicide. The commercialization of hip-hop in the late 1980s extended gangsta rap to a broader audience outside of the Black community through radio and program stations like BET and MTV. Specifically, “BET’s *Rap City* and MTV’s *Yo MTV Raps* exposed a much wider market to rap music and gave greater exposure to the rising tide of commercially successful rappers”.⁶⁵ By the mid-1990s, Black militancy expressed through gangsta rap dominated charts, and the watered-down rap songs by Vanilla Ice and MC Hammer hadn’t defined the sounds of rap music.⁶⁶

The 1990s was a decisive era for hip-hop culture and rap because the public generated a monolithic view of gangsta rap as misogynistic and violent, further feeding negative Black stereotypes. During this era, a trend emerges where complex political discussions are no longer at the forefront of rap music. Rather party anthems and economically driven music are established as general messages in songs. The flashy lifestyle of big chains and designer outfits expanded into the 1990s, and the era is celebrated for its fashion trends. Political messages

⁶⁵ Ogbar, *Hip-hop Revolution: The Culture and Politics of Rap*, pg. 109

⁶⁶ “The two most successful rappers, MC Hammer and Vanilla Ice, typified a watering down of hip-hop and commercial (White) co-optation”: Ibid, pg. 109

peaked in 1991, with 33 percent of songs containing political references, but between 1998 and 1999, chart-topping themes did not include any connections to anything inherently political (O'Connor, 2018). Despite the decline of political messages in hip-hop, some rappers steadily maintained political discourse.

The decade was defined as a culture war for its “battles rooted in ideology, religion, class difference, the social construction of racial and ethnic and gender difference”.⁶⁷ Not long after Ice Cube’s split from N.W.A. he released his debut solo album *Amerikkka’s Most Wanted* (1990). Reoccurring themes surrounding institutional racism in law enforcement, sexual irresponsibility, and misogyny were at the forefront of his gangsta mentality with influences from the Nation of Islam.⁶⁸ Ice Cube’s second studio album, *Death Certificate* (1991), shared the same sentiments but was so commercially successful that the album became the first rap compilation to reach #1 on the Billboard’s Pop Chart.⁶⁹ Songs like “True to the Game” and “Us” conveyed Black Americans’ ignorance by participating in drugs and gangs, further condemning Black Americans for part-taking in their own community’s destruction.⁷⁰ Evidence conveys Ice Cube’s Nation of Islam-styled tactics vilified Black people. Through “I Wanna Kill Sam” and “Horny Lil’ Devil,” he confronts White America for enslaving and oppressing Black people. The tensions between Black and Korean Americans were explored through “Black Korea,”; where Ice Cube highlights the mutual disdain both ethnic communities had for one another. Moreover, Ice Cube eerily predicts the 1992 LA Riots when he proclaims, “Asian-owned stores could be

⁶⁷ Donald Mitchell as quotes by Ogbar, *Hip-hop Revolution: The Culture and Politics of Rap*, pg. 110

⁶⁸ Ibid, pg. 116

⁶⁹ Ibid, pg. 116-118

⁷⁰ Ibid, pg. 117

‘burned to a crisp’.⁷¹ From 1990 to 2018, Ice Cube released critically acclaimed conscious rap music alongside various party anthems like “You Can Do It” and “We Be Clubbin.”

Ice Cube’s discography is widely known for its overtly political and misogynistic lyrics, yet his studio persona is nothing like his true character. Ice Cube’s studio persona advocates for Black men’s liberation instead of acknowledging the mutual suffrage Black men and women experience. At the same time, Ice Cube features many female artists to combat his studio persona, giving Black women an opportunity to debate feminism and oppression. Gangsta rap combined with socially conscious rap animated Black life for American popular culture, and its discourse encouraged Black Americans to reconsider their life choices. By the 2000s, Black Americans progressed out of hardship, and young Blacks considered higher education and careers. Then a trend began where, as the decades passed, the need for conscious rap declined.

The 2000s: The Movement vs. Consumerism.

As commercialism extended into the 2000s, the connection between gangsta rap and conscious rap was lost; specifically, in 2000, 2004, and 2006 there weren’t any #1 songs on the Hip-Hop Billboard Chart possessing political messages. The rise of record label influences within hip-hop insight the surge of corporate hip-hop. During this period, record labels began to control hip-hop artists’ music, thus placing politics on the backburner. Corporate machines doubted rap’s natural popularity over the dominating pop genre. Still, hip-hop producers and artists learned to manipulate radio stations through “pay-for-play, testing, call-outs, and corporate-controlled playlists”.⁷² to boost rap music.

The 2000s outlined styles for an additional region of the U.S., the Dirty South; in addition to East and West Coast rap, the Dirty South described hood lifestyles in the Southern states

⁷¹ Ibid, pg. 116

⁷² Watkins, *Hip Hop Matters Politics, Pop Culture, and the Struggle for the Soul of a Movement*, pg. 138-139

through similar tales of drugs and gang life. Considering the political messages of the East and West Coasts, Dirty South rap often were party anthems describing the “fast” life attached to stardom by measuring finances and women. These ghetto tales were overtly different from conscious rap as Black artists measured their lifestyle only by the amounts of money, jewelry, and property they owned after “getting rich.” Violence and misogyny were communicated through catchy hooks and up-tempo beats, but the focus was not on constructive critiques of Black life. Instead, these songs carried “crab in the barrel” ideologies where Black men and women concentrated on personal successes. Unifying the Black community against outer influences of racism and injustice did not concern this era’s rappers.

Elite players in hip-hop, like power labels, radio owners, and musicians, struggled to dominate pop charts and employed commercial radio and music videos to command the #1 spot.⁷³ Watkins (2005) also notes, “rap music... had surrendered much of its ambition and originality for music that cared more about servicing rather than subverting the status quo”.⁷⁴ The absence of political messages could be attributed to the desire for Black activists to “‘get past’ the ‘distraction’ of racism” and appreciate the political gains Black Americans possessed in the modern era. For instance, the inauguration of President Barack Obama in 2008; President Obama reflected a “love thy neighbor” consciousness, like Martin Luther King Jr. and James Baldwin, and he expressed compassion for White Americans the Black community hadn’t seen before. The historical physical and psychological violence committed against African Americans was unforgettable for most, considering activists advocated for reparations after Black Americans never received the “40 acres and mule” promised by the government. Martin Luther

⁷³ Ibid, pg. 139

⁷⁴ Ibid, pg. 139

King Jr. and James Baldwin's concept of love requires vulnerability and courage, and President Obama's love for White America expressed a partnership America least expected.

However, the political advancements gained during the late 2000s did not conceal the brewing issues within the Black community between men and women. Since rap was a male-dominant genre, the gender disparities between Black men and women were consistently showcased how Black feminism wasn't as popular in hip-hop. Rap's female contributions were at its peak during the 1990s and 2000s.

Black Women in the Industry.

Female contributions to hip-hop are as meaningful as the male contributions by exploring the male-dominant narratives about sexuality, violence, and materialism by infusing the traditional rap styles with indications of femineity. These male-dominant narratives endorsed misogynist themes that reinforced the attitudes regarding authenticity and realness by advocating men's domination over women; these narratives encompass the willfulness to be violent, the ability to have sexual relationships with multiple partners, and access to material resources.⁷⁵ In the late 1990s and afterward, female rappers focused their feminism on opposing the sexual hierarchy, demanding sexual equality, and reshaping Black women's imagery in entertainment discourse.⁷⁶ The feminist movement within hip-hop has tasked itself with diminishing the images dominant groups have justified degrading Black women by representing them as the jezebel, mammy, matriarch, and welfare mother.⁷⁷ Black feminism targets stereotypical images by encouraging Black women to control their lives to challenge race, gender, and classism.

⁷⁵ Ogbar, *Hip-hop Revolution: The Culture and Politics of Rap*, pg. 72-75

⁷⁶ *Ibid*, pg. 73

⁷⁷ *Ibid*, pg. 74

Early female rappers established themselves alongside MCs during the 1970s, including individual artists and rap groups. Female rap possessed limited artistic expression, and their approach to specific issues was out of the female reach. Raps about sexual exploits were destructive to the feminine image; thus, the jezebel image blossomed out of the male perception of female sexual activity. Pornography and sexual imagery were lacking between the 1970s and the 1990s, and the lack of female authorities representing feminine sexuality.⁷⁸ The jezebel and mammy caricature spread throughout the slavery era and defined Black women's role as White American territory. The justifications for the mistreatment of Black women have historical ties to the inhumane sexual exploitations of the slavery era. Further, Black women couldn't pick their partners, practice sexual health, or control their fertility. The early voices of Roxanne Roxanne, Sha Rock, Salt-n-Pepa, MC Lyte, Queen Latifah, and others praised or ridiculed Black men who subverted or reinforced portrayals of Black women.⁷⁹

During the 1990s, female artists took control of the Black female image, and rappers from this era redefined hypersexuality, feminism, and misogyny. Female artists embraced the gangsta trope contextualized by Black male artists and infused the gangsta style with sensations of feminine life, including sex, childbirth, relationships, and gender inequalities. Lil' Kim and Foxy Brown were the most successful female artists who reinvented Black femineity and proved that Black female rappers could survive around their male counterparts.⁸⁰ In 1996, male artists like Jay-Z, Nas, Notorious B.I.G., and Puff Daddy produced rap that "rejected the double standards of sexual expression"⁸¹ and supported female artists by providing them with a career platform.

⁷⁸ Assiter, Alison, and Avedon, *Bad Girls and Dirty Pictures: The Challenge to Reclaim Feminism*, pg. 3-5

⁷⁹ Ogbar, *Hip-hop Revolution: The Culture and Politics of Rap*, pg. 81-83

⁸⁰ *Ibid*, pg. 85

⁸¹ *Ibid*, pg. 85

The subversion of Black feminine stereotypes and inclusion of gangsta style introduced the “bad woman” to parallel the “badman” caricature.⁸² The bad women successfully mixed the techniques of conscious rap with gangsta rap to blend the image of the video vixen and female gangsta to sell millions of albums.⁸³ The hypersexual and violent female commercialization ushered in an era of vaguely different characterizations than previously portrayed in American entertainment. Ogbar (2007) notes:

Lil’ Kim compares herself to famous porn stars...and in several songs extolled the joys of all sorts of sexual pleasure...Referring to herself as the ‘Queen Bitch’, Kim also raps that she is a ‘kill for a nigga for my nigga by any means bitch - [a] murder scene bitch. Foxy Brown, like Kim, revels in her sexuality, but puts more emphasis on naming expensive brands in her rhymes.⁸⁴

Thus, hypersexuality becomes another vessel for authenticity in the hip-hop community.

However, Black feminists maintain that the overly sexual and violent Black female reinforces sexist, racist, and classist stereotypes in a deconstructive manner.⁸⁵ On the contrary, the avoidance of rejecting controlling images undermines the oppressive definitions by broadening women’s power to command their sexual exploits. The male agency within Black feminist rap delegates men to pleasuring women and this phenomenon has extended into the 2010s with artists like Nicki Minaj and 2020s with Cardi B and Megan thee Stallion.

The #metoo movement established more pro-feminist messages in hip-hop, and the genre took an empowering approach to Black women’s ability to love and be loved (O’Connor, 2018). In addition, to the social issues addressed in hip-hop, women were free to explore the economic benefits of the American Dream. While men maintained higher tax brackets, female artists stressed their financial gains as notable as the men. Nicki Minaj followed in the footsteps of Lil’

⁸² Ibid, pg. 84

⁸³ Ibid, pg. 84

⁸⁴ Ibid, pg. 84

⁸⁵ Ibid, pg. 86

Kim and Foxy Brown's sexual reclaim methods to dominate the rap scene in the 2010s. Nicki Minaj dominated the hip-hop and pop charts throughout the era while rapping alongside her male counterparts at Young Money. The groundbreaking sound Nicki Minaj garnished extended to the next generation of female rappers in the late 2010s, and so did her messages surrounding finances and relationships.

Cardi B's narratives of economic prosperity in "Bodak Yellow" (2018) examined the circumstances of growing up in the Bronx, New York, becoming a stripper, and finally earning her bloody shoes (a.k.a. Christian Louboutin).⁸⁶ The song's subject and success acknowledge how the American Dream is alive in the twenty-first century and extends beyond the male grasp. Megan Thee Stallion, alongside Cardi B, has produced songs reclaiming female sexuality like "W.A.P." and reminded society that women are in control of their bodies and can determine who has access to it.⁸⁷ "W.A.P." adjusted feminist women against the patriarchy and dismantled traditional views on sexuality, the conventional idea of women practicing monogamy and men possessing multiple partners.⁸⁸ Megan Thee Stallion and Cardi B took the gangsta sound and created a powerful female anthem through vulgar language and vivid imagery.⁸⁹

Black female contributions to hip-hop, specifically within conscious rap, have encouraged women to demand respect and free speech regarding their bodies. Widespread exposure to these positive messages has normalized Black female success in hip-hop and addressed deeper issues around sexism and gender disparities in American society. Black female artists are consistently evolving around the gangsta vixen caricature, thus establishing a

⁸⁶ Banh, "The Cultural Significance of "WAP"

⁸⁷ Ibid.

⁸⁸ Ibid.

⁸⁹ Ibid.

new dynamic for women and men to communicate through which endorses equality and understanding.

The 2010s: The Re-Awakening.

The inauguration of President Barack Obama in 2008 marked another year in power for the Black community. As hip-hop became legitimized as a dominant genre in American popular culture, the demand for political music was at its lowest. By 2010, top songs on the Billboard “Hot Rap Songs” chart were not inherently political (O’Connor, 2018). Over time, political rap began to creep into the hip-hop scene. As the condition of Black Americans seemed to be progressing, there were still instances of police brutality and political disenfranchisement across the country.

A study conducted on fatal police violence between 1980 to 2019 compared data from the U.S.A. National Vital Statistics Systems (N.V.S.S.), Fatal Encounters, Mapping Police Violence, and The Counted examine the high-profile police killings compared to the under-reported police violence occurring in America (Elsevier Institute on Minority Health and Health Disparities, 2021). According to the study conducted by the Elsevier Institute on Minority Health and Health Disparities (2021), between 1980 and 2019, an estimated 30,800 deaths involved police violence. This data noted mortality rates attached to police violence were at its highest against (non-Hispanic) Black people, followed by Hispanic people, (non-Hispanic) White people, and non-Hispanic people of other races (Elsevier Institute on Minority Health and Health Disparities, 2021, pg. 1243). Police brutality was no stranger to the hip-hop community. Yet, the trend of police violence against Black Americans has not decreased despite any activism or legislation outlawing racially motivated discourse. Evidence from this data acknowledges:

The police have disproportionately killed Black people at a rate 3.5 times higher than White people...The rate of fatal police violence was higher in every year for Black

Americans than for White Americans. In the U.S.A., more males died from police violence in 2019... than from environmental heat and cold exposure...testicular cancer... appendicitis... exposure to forces of nature... and sexually transmitted diseases”.⁹⁰

The injustices that controlled politically conscious rap discourse in the 1980s and the 1990s have resurfaced during the 2010s, further introducing intergenerational activism. Black youth have moved away from cultural assimilation provided by modern racism (Engel, 2019) and have stimulated neoliberalist perspectives to engage the new generation in radical ideas to combat the status quo. Engel (2019) suggests that “modern racism... considers cultural diversity within the state as solely a threat.” Unlike the hip-hop generationers, the new generation established two political movements to unify Black youth and indulge in Black empowerment. The political demonstrations that motivated Black youth were the Black Lives Matter movement and the hip-hop movement.

Megan Ming Francis and Leah Wright-Reiguer (2021) attribute the development of the Black Lives Matter Movement to the viral social media campaign of the same name. Thus, pinpoint its efforts to terminate White vigilantes and state-sanctioned violence against Black Americans. The original social media campaign began in 2013 in response to the murder of Trayvon Martin at the hands of another American citizen, his acquittal, and, subsequently, went viral on various social media platforms.⁹¹ Along with halting racial violence, the Black Lives Matter Movement also struggles to end systematic racism, capitalism, and sexism, defund the police, and reallocate funds to community programs.⁹² Francis and Wright-Reiguer (2021) note how White violence usually aims to weaken civil rights gains by establishing structural barriers to discourage Black Americans from participating in society’s social, economic, and political

⁹⁰ Elsevier Institute on Minority Health and Health Disparities, *Fatal Police Violence by Race and State in the U.S.A., 1980-2019: A Network Meta-Regression*, pg. 1247

⁹¹ Francis, Megan Ming, and Leah Wright-Rigueur. “Black Lives Matter in Historical Perspective.” *Annual Review of Law and Social Science*

⁹² Ibid.

activities. The act of political isolation and proper representation is the main target for the Black Lives Matter Movement through ideologies presented by intellectuals like Ida B Wells to Fredrick Douglass, Langston Hughes to Zora Neale, Anna Julia Cooper to Audre Lorde, and James Baldwin to Martin Luther King Jr.⁹³ The 2020 summer Black Lives Matter Protests garnered more than twenty million people from various races and backgrounds. Francis and Wright-Reiguer (2021) reported from a survey conducted by the Pew Research Center that 67% of Americans support the movement and its goals. In the case of the Black Lives Matter Movement, civil disobedience functions harmoniously by deliberating about social injustice, addressing hypocritical liberty, and acknowledging unjustified Black American deaths. Complementary to this, rappers encouraged political activism musically and physically by publicly supporting activism movements through artistic expression.

Kendrick Lamar, a rapper from Compton, California, would personify the artistic extensions of rap and Black radical ideas through his statements of rebellion, institutional corruption, and provocative imagery. As a political activist, Lamar extends racial tensions into the public's view so injustices in the Black community can be discussed as a part of American political discourse instead of an issue exclusive to Black Americans. Lamar focuses on images of defiance and empowerment to contradict elements of patriotic power, like the American flag, to shift American hope and goodness to hypocrisy and threat, following the political rap philosophers before him.⁹⁴ Lamar's Grammy award-winning album *To Pimp A Butterfly* (2015) provided self-determination and participatory ideologies that call Black Americans to action against social circumstances that have marginalized the Black community. The presence of overt racism requires physical and psychological direct action, which Lamar manifests musically and

⁹³ Lebron, *The Making of Black Lives Matter : a Brief History of an Idea*

⁹⁴ Ibid. pg. 38

in real life. Since the Black Lives Matter movement extended from the 2010s and into the 2020s, Lamar's song "Alright" from *To Pimp A Butterfly* (2015) became the movement's protest anthem (Graves, 2020). Despite the album's release in 2015, the song saw a 71 percent increase in streams in 2020 (Graves, 2020). Lamar joined the Black Lives Matter protest for George Floyd as a silent marcher and was clothed in black, also wearing a Black mask seeming to hide his identity from the public (Graves, 2020). The protest traveled from Compton's Gate Towne Center to the Martin Luther King Jr. memorial, and Lamar did not comment on his presence at the rally. Yet, his attendance legitimizes Lamar's position as a political rap activist.

The 2010s reflected an era of power on the surface due to the political representation of Black Americans in the White House; however, African Americans began producing political discourse that expressed their disdain with the end of President Obama's administration and the beginning of the Trump administration. Political voices from across America commented on the persistence of White vigilantism and state-inflicted violence on the Black community. O'Connor (2018) identifies chart-topping songs, including political messages, that rose to 25 percent in direct response to the Black Lives Matter movement and the policies and actions of the Trump administration. Kendrick Lamar wasn't the only political rap activist during the 2010s era; other songs contributed to conscious rap like YG's "FDT" (2016), Common's "Black America Again" (2016), Donald Glover's "This Is America" (2018), Nas's "Cops Shot the Kid" (2018), and many others.

Conclusion.

Hip-hop has been around for generations and will continue to evolve musically and politically. Various research studies showcase how hip-hop has been used as a source of “resistance, motivation, information, and entertainment” (Bonnette 2015). This research paper analyzed the political effects of rap on the Black community throughout the decades. The result of this paper acknowledges many aspects of Black culture within America. The political contributions of artists like Afrika Bambaataa, N.W.A., Public Enemy, Ice Cube, Kendrick Lamar, and other artists have influenced generations of Black Americans from 1965 to 2022. Hip-hop’s political implications have extended beyond American borders as political rap has appeared worldwide in Russia and Asia. Debates surrounding hip-hop culture’s ability to subvert and reinforce stereotypes have questioned rap’s ability to be constructive. Black-on-Black street violence expressed lyrically has proven detrimental to political rap’s success. Events like the murders of socially conscious rappers Nipsey Hussle and Young Dolph have supported the idea that hip-hop is overtly violent considering the genre’s themes.

The hip-hop movement has maintained a neoliberalist perspective, and, in 2010, many rappers returned to politically conscious activism in music and endorsed protest movements like Black Lives Matter. Hip-hop is an extension of Black life into American popular culture. Yet, social and political institutions still neglect the Black person, despite non-Black individuals infiltrating rap music. Political rap will continue to be a part of hip-hop culture, and new political rap activists will step forward to express the Black community’s values and desires for the future.

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